

Outcome of the SATCON1 Online Workshop

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In May 2019, the astronomical community was somewhat stunned at the brightness of the streaks of 60 SpaceX Starlink satellites seen in images. This underscored how we are experiencing a major intersection of technologies between deep, wide-field sky surveys and potentially large numbers of low-Earth-orbiting satellites (LEOsats), also known as constellation satellites. For instance, with potentially tens of thousands of Starlink satellites, SpaceX's capability to provide internet service to billions of people worldwide has definite merits. At the same time, there is a tremendous amount of new technology coming online within the field of astronomy in the next decade that will substantially increase humanity's understanding of the Universe. However, observatories require a dark night sky to uncover the secrets behind some of the most fundamental questions about the nature of our Universe. Prime examples of these new technologies are Vera C. Rubin Observatory and the 30-meter telescopes, coming online in the next decade. For reasons of expense, maintenance, and instrumentation, such facilities cannot be launched into space. Ground-based astronomy is, and will remain, vital and relevant.

The collective response from the astronomy community to the emergence of the constellation satellites commenced this Northern Hemisphere spring, as 46 experts from around the world came together under an NSF grant to NOIRLab. As part of four working groups, they were tasked with studying the impacts of satellite constellations on astronomy, and determining possible mitigation steps that could feasibly be implemented by observatories, satellite operators, and funding agencies. Connie Walker (NSF's NOIRLab) and Jeff Hall (Lowell Observatory) co-chaired the Scientific Organizing Committee (SOC). The four working groups (WGs) focused on the following areas: observations, simulations, mitigations and metrics. They were led by Lori Allen (NOIRLab), Pat Seitzer (U. Michigan), Tony Tyson (UC Davis/Rubin Observatory) and Richard Green (Steward Observatory/U. Arizona), respectively. In about a month each group had completed its report.

Figure 1. Cover of the report "Impact of Satellite Constellations on Optical Astronomy and Recommendations Toward Mitigations" from the SATCON1 workshop. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/AAS)

A workshop called SATCON1 was organized jointly by NSF's NOIRLab and the American Astronomical Society (AAS), and held online from 29 June to 2 July 2020. It focused on technical aspects of the impact of existing and planned large satellite constellations on optical and infrared astronomy. At the workshop, members of the working groups presented in a zoom webinar and discussions followed. There were 250 attendees from industry and astronomy.

The goals of SATCON1 were to better quantify the scientific impacts of huge ensembles of LEOsats contaminating astronomical observations and to explore possible ways to minimize those impacts. The remarks from the discussions were included in revisions and a few weeks later a final main summary report and an appendix with the working group reports were released at the start of a press briefing. The two parts of the final report can be found [here](#) (main document) and [here](#) (appendices).

The report concludes that the effects of large satellite constellations on astronomical research and on the human experience of the night sky range from "negligible" to "extreme." At the press briefing organized by NOIRLab and AAS on 25 August 2020, the chairs of the SOC and WGs presented the highlights of the findings and the recommendations of the studies by the four working groups. These are summarized below.

Findings

Finding 1

The projected surface density of bright satellites in constellations is greatest near the horizon and during twilight. For this reason, LEO constellations disproportionately impact science programs that require twilight observations, such as searches for near-Earth objects (NEOs), distant Solar System objects, and optical counterparts of fleeting gravitational wave sources. Depending on constellation design, LEOsats can also be visible deep into the night, broadening the impact to encompass all astronomical programs. We find that the worst-case constellation designs prove extremely impactful to the most severely affected science programs. For the less affected programs, the impact ranges from negligible to significant, requiring novel software and hardware efforts in an attempt to avoid satellites and remove trails from images.

Figure 2. A simulated all-sky plot of trails of 47,708 illuminated LEOsats over a 10-minute time period as seen from Rubin Observatory in Chile with the altitude of the Sun at -18.4 degrees. Zenith is at the center, north is up and east is left. The trails are bunched due to populating the orbital planes. The trail-free region is caused by the Earth's shadow. (Credit: P. Yoachim, U. Washington/ Rubin Observatory)

We find two step-functions in impact based on the brightness of the satellites: naked-eye visibility and instrument sensor calibration range. If satellites are visible to the naked eye, the scope of impact expands to include non-professional, unaided-eye observers including amateur astronomers and astrophotographers, and possibly indigenous peoples and members of religions that observe the sky for calendar-keeping. Satellites whose apparent brightnesses are below unaided-eye visibility can have a much more severe impact on astronomical science if they are bright enough to cause non-correctable artifacts in the camera sensors. For fainter satellites, of course, the trail itself remains and must be dealt with. In the cases where it might be impossible to fully mask or remove trails, a bright enough satellite could induce systematic errors impacting some science investigations.

Satellites below 600 km (373 miles)

LEOsat constellations below 600 km are visible for a few hours per night around astronomical twilight from observatories at middle latitudes, but they are in Earth's shadow and invisible for several hours per night around local solar midnight, with some satellites visible during the transitions. This visibility pattern causes these constellations to most heavily impact twilight observers (see the examples mentioned above). Since these orbits are closer to Earth, satellites at these altitudes will be brighter than the same satellites would be at higher orbital altitudes. The reduced range makes them more likely to exceed the unaided-eye brightness threshold if operators fail to design with this criterion in mind.

Satellites above 600 km

Satellites above 600 km are an even greater concern to astronomers because they include all the impacts mentioned above, but can also be illuminated all night long. Full-night illumination causes these high-altitude constellations to impact a larger set of astronomical programs.

Finding 2

Approaches to mitigate LEOsat impacts on optical-NIR astronomy fall into six main categories.

1. Launch fewer or no LEOsat constellations. This is the only option identified that can achieve zero impact.
2. Deploy satellites at orbital altitudes no higher than ~ 600 km
3. Darken satellites by lowering their albedo, shading reflected sunlight, or some combination thereof.
4. Control each satellite's attitude in orbit so that it reflects less sunlight to Earth.
5. Remove or mask satellite trails and their effects in images.
6. Avoid satellite trails with the use of accurate ephemerides.

Recommendations

1. For Observatories

Recommendation 1

Support development of a software application available to the general astronomy community to identify, model,

subtract, and mask satellite trails in images on the basis of user-supplied parameters.

Recommendation 2

Support development of a software application for observation planning available to the general astronomy community that predicts the time and projection of satellite transits through an image, given celestial position, time of night, exposure length, and field of view, based on the public database of ephemerides. Current simulation work provides a strong basis for the development of such an application.

Recommendation 3

Support selected detailed simulations of the effects on data analysis systematics and data reduction signal-to-noise impacts of masked trails on scientific programs affected by satellite constellations. Aggregation of results should identify any lower thresholds for the brightness or rate of occurrence of satellite trails that would significantly reduce their negative impact on the observations.

2. For Constellation Operators

Recommendation 4

LEOsat operators should perform adequate laboratory Bi-directional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) measurements as part of their satellite design and development phase. This would be particularly effective when paired with a reflectance simulation analysis.

Recommendation 5

Reflected sunlight ideally should be slowly varying with orbital phase as recorded by high etendue (effective area \times field of view), large-aperture ground-based telescopes to be fainter than $7.0 V_{\text{mag}} + 2.5 \times \log(r_{\text{orbit}} / 550 \text{ km})$, equivalent to $44 \times (550 \text{ km} / r_{\text{orbit}})$ watts/steradian.

Recommendation 6

Operators must make their best effort to avoid specular reflection (flares) in the direction of observatories. If such flares do occur, accurate timing information from ground-based observing will be required for avoidance.

Recommendation 7

Pointing avoidance by observatories is achieved most readily if the immediate post-launch satellite configuration is clumped as tightly as possible consistent with safety, affording rapid passage of the train through a given pointing area. Also, satellite attitudes should be adjusted to minimize reflected light on the ground track.

3. For Observatories and Operators in Collaboration

Recommendation 8

Support an immediate coordinated effort for optical observations of LEOsat constellation members, to characterize both slowly and rapidly varying reflectivity and the effectiveness of experimental mitigations. Such observations require facilities spread over latitude and longitude to capture Sun-angle-dependent effects. In the longer term, support a comprehensive satellite constellation observing network with uniform observing and data reduction protocols for feedback to operators and astronomical programs. Mature constellations will have the added complexity of deorbiting of the units and on-orbit aging, requiring ongoing monitoring.

Recommendation 9

Determine the cadence and quality of updated positional information or processed telemetry, distribution, and predictive modeling required to achieve substantial improvement (by a factor of about 10) in publicly available cross-track positional determination.

Recommendation 10

Adopt a new standard format for publicly available ephemerides beyond two-line-elements (TLEs) in order to include covariances and other useful information. The application noted in Recommendation 2 should be compatible with this format and include the appropriate errors.

The next workshop, SATCON2, which will tackle the significant issues of policy and regulation, is tentatively planned for early to mid-2021.